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AI in Marketing in Reference of Indian Market: Artificial Intelligence and Its Application in Marketing

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Abstract

Human race has evolved considerably from ancient Mesopotamian civilization to present modern era. The changes have been revolutionary and have deeply impacted our socio and economic life. The metamorphosis of human life has been fuelled by radical changes in technology to aid the process. Today we are the verge of another technological revolution which in long run will change the whole socio-economic fabric of our system. Artificial Intelligence (AI) works on the pattern of human brain and its learning and decision-making skills are much more accurate than human beings. Organizations across the globe have realized that AI can help them to identify their target market and offer better satisfaction at reduced cost. Since the whole operation of AI based on algorithm, data mining is an integrated part of whole process. With intermittent fluctuation in consumer expectations and the rising cost of communicating and acquisition of the customer more and more companies are exploring alternate route to reach out to customer and AI offers them a one stop solution for all their requirements. Though the privacy and ethical issue is still debatable, the digitalization of marketing activities has boosted its growth. This paper attempts to explore the usage of AI by in marketing activities and its future applications.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology, Algorithm, Consumers, Data mining, Digitalization

Introduction

Marketing is the lifeline of any business activity. The whole crux of marketing lies in reaching out to the potential customer and full fill his needs. Now this sounds simple but actually it is very complicated and costly process with no guarantee of any fixed returns. Organizations consistently try to explore new routes to excite the consumers in a cost-effective manner. Though Communication process has witnessed rapid changes with advent of technology still it lacks the accuracy and ROI is haphazard. The internet boom in India has opened various avenues for doing business and has propelled the country to become the largest hub for Start-ups. Al most 90%

of the start-ups are technology-based enterprises with average age of founder below 30yrs. With meticulous planning and algorithm-based database they were able to invoke the interest of global venture Capitalist who pumped millions of dollars in them. The internet boom has change the dynamics of doing business and the percent share of digital marketing has been increasing rapidly in organizations' budget. More and more companies are becoming data centric as they are finding it easier and more responsive to reach the customer through online media. Even the consumer are becoming more receptive towards digital communication channel as they are spending more time browsing net rather than watching tv or reading newspapers. With concept of smart homes gaining popularity the consumer dependence of Tech based products is increasing day by day. Amazon Alexa or Apple Siri are providing hand on experience to the consumers of how Artificial Intelligence can assist in managing our daily tasks. Though it is still in nascent stage as the competition intensifies more and more firms shall shift from traditional to AI based approach and the companies shall be forced to migrate from generic solutions. Since AI can have long term consequences on profitability firms needs to increasingly consider the consequences of rating lower in customer interaction and satisfaction index by not adopting the modern approach.

Due to significant growth in online retailing and competition, business organisations need to migrate away from traditional solutions to modern solutions. Same is the case of service marketing, quality of service not only the single criteria to evaluate, it also include the quality of experience of customer related to service. Studies states that inclusion of new technology will help in personalising and enhancing the satisfaction level of the customers.

If we look back at history, there is no denial that people are emotional dependent on technology. It result into increase in the use of digital technology, comfort level between user and technology. This optimistic relationship can be used to enhance customer experience.

The introduction of new algorithms, fast processing cloud based data is making it possible for all the business organization to experiment with artificial intelligence. In the context of sales and marketing operations it is very early days in the domain of artificial intelligence. Marketing and sales operations mostly use artificial intelligence on advertisement and media. Many research is done on applicability of artificial intelligence in sales and marketing and it is found that most of the present experiment is happening in the field of programmatic advertisement, marketing automation, increase customer service. Artificial intelligence is also used in email marketing, lead generation, sales forecasting, cross selling etc.

Artificial intelligence and modern marketing: Marketing operations are utilizing artificial intelligence platforms in various ways.

Marketing Intelligence: Artificial intelligence helps in excelling at clustering and processing massive volume of data from different sources, which include data management platform, data warehouse and other sources. Input of data can be collected from various sources and relationship can be build and make predictions, which is impossible without technology. Marketers also use artificial intelligence for business intelligence, marketing research and accurate forecasting.

Generating lead and acquisition of customer: Artificial intelligence solutions are also capable of generating lead, which helps in acquisition of more customer.

Market optimization: Artificial intelligence applications can be utilize for media buying, content designing. Applications include advertisement programming and marketing campaign optimization and analysis.

Customer experience Management: Among artificial intelligence technologies like call centers, bots and virtual digital assistant, smarter search interface and recommender system, which is significantly contributing in excelling customer support.

Creation of content: Many industries using artificial intelligence driven platform to create content, on demand advertisement. Promotional material, websites and other publish content. It include automated writing and image and video creation for specific target audience.

Practices for Implementation of Artificial Intelligence: Modern technology has significant impact on productivity of a business organization. The only question is how best technology is implemented. Following are the few principle to be considered for effective implementation.

Training and feedback: It is very important to have trust to create a collaborative environment between the marketers. Relevant training is essential to build trust and create an environment which is driven by technology.

Monitor each employee’s interaction and use of modern technologies: Every employee has different engagement level with regard to technology. Organization need to observe and encourage usage of new technology by minimizing misuse and human errors.

Select the right machine learning tool that maximize productivity: Selection of right technology, which can enhanced productivity for the business organization, plays a pivotal role in the success of business process. Technology should be risk free and user friendly for the marketer, which will encourage the market to think aggressively about the usage of technology in their marketing process.

Work with vendors to set up control and prevent malfunction: Transparency is a virtue that significantly contribute towards building trust and avoiding errors. Any error can harm the brand reputation and decrease revenue generation. It necessitate a sound control mechanism to be in place to prevent any malfunction.

Artificial Intelligence Practices at India’s Top e-Commerce Firms

Internet penetration has increase significantly in the last decade. According to Boston Consulting Group, internet users increase up to 550 million in 2018 from 190 million in June 2014. India became the second largest smartphone users in the world after US. All the E-commerce companies in India is feeling the heat of competition. Most of the companies injecting artificial intelligence platforms to create good quality product, smarter logistics, and target right demographics.

Flipkart: In 2018, flipkart joined hand with Microsoft to provide improve service to digital shopping service. The main idea behind this is to deliver innovative merchandise, advertisement, marketing and customer service.

Project MIRA: It is a digital initiative by flipkart to engage customers before they make purchase decision, to prevent the rate of returns by asking few simple question in artificial intelligence platforms.

Amazon India: The Company has already injected USD 2 billion in India. Company believed that artificial intelligence helps in smart e-commerce, enhanced operation efficiency and help in meeting customer expectation. Amazon India has used artificial intelligence technologies in various areas:

Correcting address: Due to the unstructured nature of postal address issues like failed deliveries, missing delivery date, and delayed delivery are found very frequently. Artificial intelligence technologies helps in detecting false address, correcting city pin code mismatches and provide suggestion to users to correct address.

Catalog quality: Amazon India is using machine learning technology to reduce the defect in Catalog like brand, colour, and image quality.

Myntra: The Company is mainly implementing artificial intelligence in three aspect product, experience and logistics.

Product: Myntra is using an artificial intelligence platform called as “RAPID” to identify current fashion trends. It is done with the help of sales analysis. Another technology called Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), which helps in creating similar but not same product. Earlier this year Myntra has launch a T-shirt design which is fully design by machine.

Experience: According to Institute of Business in Global Context, online payment transaction mostly failed due to digital incompetency and poor IT infrastructure. By using best payment gateways payment needs can be met. On the other hand Myntra is applying artificial intelligence on making recommendation to customers by analysing purchase behaviour of the customers.

Logistics: One of the biggest concern of Myntra related to logistics is return system. A platform called “SABRE” is used in Myntra to detect the Genuine returns, based on past purchase behaviour of the customer. It is very useful to resolve the problems of return.

The Relationship between Marketing and Artificial Intelligence: If we look back at past, business organisations hesitant to incorporate artificial intelligence into their strategies. Things have changed confidence level among marketers for artificial intelligence application has significantly increase. The main reason for this is the optimistic result towards business process efficiency. Digital marketing is an area where the presence of artificial intelligence is felt strongly. Some of the key areas where technology can boost digital marketing in 2018.

Personalizing user experience to a greater extent: It can be done with the help of clustering big customer data and then identifying individual behaviour and interest. Chat box is another platform that can enhance user experience. It is programmed to provide a platform for the customers to interact with business organisations.

Make Your Decision Simpler & Easier With Predictive Marketing: Each time a user browses on the internet; new information is generated and picked up for AI analysis. This information will reveal data like user wants, behaviours, and future actions. Supported this data, promoting is optimized to produce the foremost relevant data. Social media reaching conjointly reveals personal data regarding the prospect creating it straightforward for marketers to make a targeted campaign.

This additional reduces the sales-cycle because the relevant data is bimanual over to customers on a silver plate. This “predictive” campaigns will considerably cut back client analysis on the merchandise and makes deciding easier. As for marketers, they will still analyse the buyer| through information and even build the customer return!

This type of AI-enabled algorithms can challenge the present ‘hotshots’ like SEO during a large means. With AI powering the digital promoting initiatives from ground level, possibilities of trends like SEO, banner ads turning into obsolete square measure high. After all, United Nations agency wants SEO and web site traffic after you have an in depth report of your prospect?

Using image recognition to get maximum ROI: Previously, image recognition was confined to characteristic isolated objects in a picture. However with AI – enabled package, it’s currently potential to induce a close description of a picture. Amazon’s latest production Amazon Recognition will truly acknowledge human faces, emotions concerned and determine objects. This technology may be utilized in varied ways that for varied sectors. For banking and monetary sector, AI-enabled image recognition may be leveraged for quicker payment processes and enhance client security. Social media may be a large supply of pictures.

Social media has continually been biased towards visual content as tweets with pictures receive a hundred and fifty additional tweets and Facebook posts with pictures receive two.3X times additional engagement. The planet population along shares three.25 billion photos every day per this analysis. This large quantity of pictures may be leveraged by AI to grasp shopper patterns, behaviors, and needs. AI package can seek for pictures in social media and compare it to an oversized image library to draw conclusions.

For example, a snack manufacturer will map their complete against the massive assortment of photos in social media and perceive the client demographics reminiscent of cohort, gender etc., and conjointly geographical potentials reminiscent of if the snack was consumed additional at the beach, park, supermarkets, theaters so on. This can facilitate to align the promoting ways so as to extract most come back on Investment.

Conclusion

Thanks to social media stretch and massive knowledge, we tend to currently apprehend customers higher than we tend to ever did. Computer science and its associated technologies ought to bring marketers and customers nearer within the returning years. Customers have a stronger understanding of a product and marketers have a stronger understanding of shoppers. With computer science because the connecting link between them, it'd be fascinating to envision however digital promoting seems in 2018. Optimized higher cognitive process, higher sales-cycle and 'predictive' shopping for and commerce processes are sure-shot outcomes of this robotic war. However this point each customers and makes would air the winning facet. So let's wait and see however marketers are maneuvering this extremely fatal weapon to multiply sales, strengthening the pipeline and to urge real near to the shoppers.

References

- “The role of Artificial intelligence in E- commerce sector and its scope in future”, (2017), march 31, Deccan Chronicle.
- “Global artificial intelligence opportunities on retail”, (2017), April 04, Report thinker.
- Neff Chriss. (2017), “3 practical way Artificial Intelligence can enhance marketing creativity right now, It is already in our lives than we realize”, April 03, 2017, Adweek.
- Winston Henry Patrick, “Artificial Intelligence”, Third Edition, *Pearson Education*.